

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Performance of lowland transplanted sali (winter) rice varieties under late planting in Assam, India

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In flood-prone areas of Assam, transplanting of sali (tall or semidwarf winter) rice is sometimes impossible at the normal time (Jul-Aug) because of floods, forcing farmers to transplant older seedlings after the floodwater recedes. To compensate for low tillering from the aged seedlings, farmers transplant 4-6 seedlings/hill instead of 2-3 at a closer spacing. But with the monsoon retreating, the crop often suffers from insufficient soil moisture late in the season.

We evaluated yield performance of three photoperiod-insensitive semidwarf cultivars, IET10334, IET9757, and IET7251; two photoperiod-sensitive semidwarf cultivars, Biraj and Kmj 1-52-3; and two photoperiod-sensitive tall cultivars, Andrewsali and Monoharsali, during 1990-92 under two normal and two late transplanting dates (TPD).

In both years, seeds were sown on 17 Jul. Seedlings were transplanted at 25, 40, 55, and 70 d after sowing (DAS) on 11 and 26 Aug and 10 and 25 Sep, respectively. A split-plot design with four replications was used with TPD as main plots and cultivars as subplots.

For normal transplanting (11 and 26 Aug), 2-3 seedlings/hill were transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing; for late transplanting (10 and 25 Sep), 4-6 seedlings/hill were transplanted at 15- × 10-cm spacing.

The soil was a clay loam with pH 5.8, 0.7% organic C, 65 kg available P/ha, and 115 kg available K/ha. Fertilizers were applied at 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha.

Mean yield was greater in 1991-92 than in 1990-91 (see table), perhaps because of a more favorable cessation of the wet season. Rainfall during Nov-Dec was greater in 1991 (120.7 mm) than in 1990 (71.8 mm).

Grain yield (t/ha) and duration (d) of some sali rice varieties as influenced by transplanting dates in Assam, India, 1990-92.

Cultivar	Transplanting date (TPD) ^a				Mean
	11 Aug (25 DAS)	26 Aug (40 DAS)	10 Sep (55 DAS)	25 Sep (70 DAS)	
<i>1990-91</i>					
Monoharsali	2.8 (130) ^b	2.7 (134)	2.0 (137)	1.9 (137)	2.3
Andrewsali	2.7 (130)	2.4 (133)	2.3 (137)	2.2 (137)	2.4
IET10334	2.2 (138)	1.7 (149)	1.5 (164)	1.3 (172)	1.7
IET9757	2.7 (139)	1.8 (148)	1.5 (175)	0.1 (178)	1.5
IET7251	2.8 (131)	2.5 (137)	2.2 (146)	1.8 (156)	2.3
Kmj 1-52-3	2.4 (131)	2.2 (134)	2.1 (137)	2.1 (148)	2.2
Biraj	2.8 (131)	2.3 (134)	2.1 (137)	2.0 (143)	2.3
Mean	2.6	2.2	2.0	1.6	2.5
<i>1991-92</i>					
Monoharsali	4.2 (130)	4.0 (131)	3.9 (136)	3.2 (142)	3.8
Andrewsali	4.6 (126)	4.2 (128)	3.9 (135)	3.6 (137)	4.1
IET10334	4.0 (137)	3.8 (145)	2.2 (161)	0.8 (167)	2.7
IET9757	3.7 (142)	2.3 (150)	0.2 (175)	0.1 (177)	1.6
IET7251	3.9 (131)	3.3 (140)	2.9 (151)	0.3 (155)	2.6
Kmj 1-52-3	4.0 (130)	3.7 (135)	3.6 (137)	3.2 (145)	3.6
Biraj	3.7 (130)	3.9 (134)	3.7 (136)	3.2 (145)	3.6
Mean	4.0	3.6	2.9	2.1	3.7
<i>LSD for yield</i> (0.05)		<i>1990-91</i>	<i>1991-92</i>		
TPD		0.08	0.11		
CV		0.10	0.22		
CV within a TPD		0.21	0.45		
TPD within the same or different CV		0.20	0.42		

^aSown on 17 Jul. ^bDuration in parentheses.

The main effects of TPD and cultivars on grain yield were significant (see table). Grain yield decreased significantly with delay in transplanting. Andrewsali significantly outyielded Monoharsali, Kmj 1-52-3, and Biraj, which in turn significantly outyielded the three IET cultivars.

The interaction between TPD and cultivars was significant, with greater yield reduction in the case of photoperiod-insensitive cultivars than for photoperiod-sensitive cultivars. With late transplanting in 1991-92, Andrewsali, Monoharsali, Kmj 1-52-3, and Biraj significantly outyielded the three IET cultivars.

Delay in transplanting significantly increased crop duration (see table), especially for the photoperiod-insensitive cultivars. Extended crop duration resulted in decreased grain yield, presumably because plants were exposed to greater water stress at the grain-filling stage.

Thus, in flood-prone areas of Assam, tall photoperiod-sensitive cultivars, such as Andrewsali, are favored. If floods delay transplanting, such cultivars are less susceptible to delay in flowering and the likely reduction in grain yield due to terminal drought stress. ■